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FEATURES OF THE EXCHANGE OF NITROGENOUS METABOLITES AND ELECTROLYTES UNDER DIFFERENT OPTIONS OF URIC ACID EXCHANGE IN RATS

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ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ОБМІНУ АЗОТИСТИХ МЕТАБОЛІТІВ ТА ЕЛЕКТРОЛІТІВ ЗА РІЗНИХ ВАРІАНТІВ ОБМІНУ СЕЧОВОЇ КИСЛОТИ У ЩУРІВ

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБМЕНА АЗОТИСТЫХ МЕТАБОЛИТОВ И ЭЛЕКТРОЛИТОВ ПО РАЗЛИЧНЫМ ВАРИАНТАМ ОБМЕНА МОЧЕВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ У КРЫС

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Summary/Резюме

Background. We previously identified 4 variants-clusters of uricemia and uricosuria both in rats and in humans. It was shown that the clusters differ from each other in the constellation of immune, autonomic and endocrine parameters, which correlate with uricemia and uricosuria. The aim of this study was to identify the electrolytes and nitrogenous metabolites, the combination of which differentiates previously formed quantitative and qualitative variants of uric acid metabolism in rats.

Materials and Methods. Experiment was performed on 60 healthy female Wistar rats 220-300 g. The plasma and urine levels of the uric acid, urea, creatinine, calcium, phosphates, chloride, magnesium, sodium and potassium (also in erythrocytes) as well as glucose (in plasma only) were determined.

Results. 10 metabolic parameters characteristic of four variants of uric acid exchange were identified: the concentration of glucose, urea, phosphates, magnesium and potassium in plasma, and the latter in erythrocytes, as well as the excretion of creatinine, urea, phosphates and calcium with urine. The accuracy of discrimination of clusters based on the totality of this metabolic constellation together with uricemia is 95 %. The cumulative determining influence of the parameters of uric acid exchange (due to the significant advantage of uricosuria over uricemia) on the constellation of metabolic parameters is 56 %. Diuresis and excretion of phosphates and potassium are subject to the maximum positive determination from the side of uric acid; excretion of calcium, creatinine and urea are determined to a lesser extent; levels of creatinine, urea and potassium in the plasma are even less, and magnesiumuria is subject to the minimum determination. **Conclusion.** Uric acid is naturally associated with the state of electrolytes and nitrogenous metabolites exchange in healthy female rats.

Keywords: *uricemia, uricosuria, electrolytes, nitrogenous metabolites, relationships, female rats.*

Введение. Ранее мы идентифицировали 4 варианта — кластеры урикемии и урикозурии как у крыс, так и у людей. Было показано, что кластеры отличаются друг от друга констелляцией иммунных, вегетативных и эндокринных параметров коррелирующих с урикемией и урикозурией. *Целью* данного исследования было идентифицировать электролиты и азотистые метаболиты, совокупность которых дифференцирует ранее сложившиеся количественные и качественные варианты метаболизма мочевой кислоты у крыс.

Материалы и методы. Эксперимент проводили на 60 здоровых самках крыс Вистар массой 220-300 г. В плазме и моче определяли уровень мочевой кислоты, мочевины, креатинина, кальция, фосфатов, хлоридов, магния, натрия и калия (также в эритроцитах), а также глюкозы (плазме).

Результаты. Выявлены 10 метаболических параметров, характерных для четырех вариантов обмена мочевой кислоты: концентрация глюкозы, мочевины, фосфатов, магния и калия в плазме крови и последнего в эритроцитах, а также экскреция креатинина, мочевины, фосфатов и кальция с мочой. Точность различия кластеров по совокупности этой метаболической констелляции вместе с урикемией составляет 95 %. Кумулятивное определяющее влияние параметров обмена мочевой кислоты (из-за значительного преимущества урикозурии над урикемией) на констелляцию метаболических параметров составляет 56 %. Диурез и экскреция фосфатов и калия при максимально положительном определении со стороны мочевой кислоты; выведение кальция, креатинина и мочевины определяются в меньшей степени; уровни креатинина, мочевины и калия в плазме еще меньше, а магнийурия подлежит минимальному определению.

Вывод. Мочевая кислота естественным образом связана с состоянием обмена электролитов и азотистых метаболитов у здоровых самок крыс.

Ключевые слова: урикемия, урикозурия, электролиты, азотистые метаболиты, взаимосвязи, крысные самки.

Вступ. Раніше ми ідентифікували 4 варіанти — кластери урикемії та урикозурії як у щурів, так і у людей. Було показано, що кластери відрізняються один від одного констеляцією імунних, вегетативних та ендокринних параметрів, які корелюють з урикемією та урикозурією. Метою даного дослідження було ідентифікувати електроліти та азотисті метаболіти, сукупність яких диференціює раніше сформовані кількісні та якісні варіанти метаболізму сечової кислоти у щурів.

Матеріали та методи. Експеримент проводили на 60 здорових самках щурів Вістар масою 220-300 г. У плазмі та сечі визначали рівень сечової кислоти, сечовини, креатиніну, кальцію, фосфатів, хлоридів, магнію, натрію та калію (також в еритроцитах), а також глюкози (лише в плазмі).

Результати. Виявлено 10 метаболічних параметрів, характерних для чотирьох варіантів обміну сечової кислоти: концентрація глюкози, сечовини, фосфатів, магнію і калію в плазмі крові та останнього в еритроцитах, а також екскреція креатиніну, сечовини, фосфатів і кальцію з сечею. Точність розрізнення кластерів за сукупністю цієї метаболічної констеляції разом з урикемією становить 95 %. Кумулятивний визначальний вплив параметрів обміну сечової кислоти (через значну перевагу урикозурії над урикемією) на констеляцію метаболічних параметрів становить 56 %. Діурез і екскреція фосфатів і калію за умови максимально позитивного визначення з боку сечової кислоти; виведення кальцію, креатиніну і сечовини визначаються в меншій мірі; рівні креатиніну, сечовини і калію в плазмі ще менше, а магнійурія підлягає мінімальному визначенню.

Висновок. Сечова кислота природним чином пов'язана зі станом обміну електролітів і азотистих метаболітів у здорових самок щурів.

Ключові слова: урикемія, урикозурія, електроліти, азотисті метаболіти, взаємозв'язки, самки щурів.

Introduction

We previously identified 4 variants-clusters of uricemia and uricosuria both in rats [1-3] and in humans [4-6]. Using the method of discriminant analysis, it was shown that the clusters differ from each

other in the constellation of immune [3,5,6], autonomic and endocrine [7] parameters, which to one degree or another correlate with uricemia and uricosuria. Even earlier in our laboratory, the connection of uricemia with parameters of electrolytes and nitrogenous exchange in urological patients was revealed [8]. Therefore, the aim of this study was to identify the electrolytes and nitrogenous metabolites, the combination of which differentiates previously formed quantitative and qualitative variants of uric acid metabolism in rats.

Таблиця 1

Summary of the step-by-step analysis of metabolic variables ranked by the Λ criterion

VariableEnter	F to enter	p-value	Lambda	F-value	p-value
Uricemia	45,6	0,000000	0,290	45,6	0,000000
Magnesium Plasma	9,9	0,000026	0,189	23,9	0,000000
Phosphates Plasma	5,6	0,002132	0,144	17,8	0,000000
Phosphates Excretion	5,1	0,003749	0,112	15,1	0,000000
Potassium Plasma	4,3	0,008442	0,090	13,4	0,000000
Urea Plasma	3,5	0,021897	0,074	12,1	0,000000
Potassium Erythrocytes	2,7	0,055483	0,064	11,0	0,000000
Creatinine Excretion	1,7	0,173862	0,058	9,9	0,000000
Glucose Plasma	1,2	0,330486	0,054	9,0	0,000000
Urea Excretion	1,1	0,349804	0,050	8,2	0,000000
Calcium Excretion	1,2	0,308472	0,047	7,6	0,000000

Table 2

Standardized and unstandardized coefficients and constants for discriminant metabolic variables

Variable	Standardized Coefficients		
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3
Uricemia	-0,975	-0,230	0,094
Magnesium Plasma	-0,267	0,589	-0,682
Phosphates Plasma	-0,539	0,711	0,593
Phosphates Excretion	0,078	0,117	1,408
Potassium Plasma	-0,447	0,548	0,167
Urea Plasma	0,162	0,624	0,042
Potassium Erythrocytes	-0,386	-0,333	0,127
Creatinine Excretion	-0,099	0,359	-0,736
Glucose Plasma	-0,147	-0,320	0,002
Urea Excretion	-0,963	-0,206	-0,629
Calcium Excretion	0,527	0,159	0,310
Variable	Raw Coefficients		
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3
Uricemia	-0,0040	-0,0010	0,0004
Magnesium Plasma	-0,6112	1,3477	-1,5617
Phosphates Plasma	-1,2330	1,6275	1,3584
Phosphates Excretion	0,0149	0,0223	0,2690
Potassium Plasma	-0,5778	0,7096	0,2156
Urea Plasma	0,0577	0,2219	0,0150
Potassium Erythrocytes	-0,0617	-0,0532	0,0202
Creatinine Excretion	-0,0214	0,0774	-0,1585
Glucose Plasma	-0,1864	-0,4069	0,0028
Urea Excretion	-0,0056	-0,0012	-0,0036
Calcium Excretion	0,2278	0,0689	0,1339
Constant	12,9270	-0,7885	-3,6300

Material and methods

Experiment was performed on 60 healthy female Wistar rats 220-300 g. Of these, 10 remained naïve, while others received drinking water of various compositions during the week. The day after the completion of the drinking course animals were placed in individual with perforated bottom for collecting daily urine. The experiment was completed

by decapitation of rats in order to collect as much blood as possible. The plasma and urine levels of the

uric acid (uricase method), creatinine (by Jaffe's color reaction by Popper's method), urea (urease method by reaction with phenolhypochlorite), glucose (in plasma only; glucose-oxidase method), calcium (by reaction with arsenase III), phosphates (phosphate-molybdate method), magnesium (by reaction with colgamite), chloride (mercury-rhodanidine by flaming photometry) method), sodium and potassium (both also in erythrocytes; were determined. The analyzes were carried out according to the instructions described in the manual [9].

The analyzers "Pointe-180" ("Scientific", USA) and "Reflotron" (Boehringer Mannheim, BRD) were used with appropriate sets and a flaming spectrophotometer "СФ-47".

Digital material is statistically processed on a computer using the software package "Statistica 5.5".

Results and Discussion

The discriminant analysis procedure [10] included in the model, in addition to uricemia, 10 variables characteristic of four clusters (Tables 1). They represent the concentration of glucose, urea, phos-

phates, magnesium and potassium in plasma, and the latter in erythrocytes, as well as the excretion of creatinine, urea, phos-

Table 3

Correlations between metabolic variables and roots, centroids of clusters and Z-values of clusters

	Correlations Variables-Roots			S+Un+	Sn+U+	SnUn+	S-Un-
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3				
Root 1 (71,9 %)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-3,39	-1,05	+0,06	+3,30
Uricemia	-0,663	-0,325	0,101	+2,10	+0,59	-0,32	-1,18
Uricosuria	currently not in the model			+0,24	+0,17	-0,05	-0,45
Creatinine Excretion	-0,133	0,168	0,077	+0,74	+0,90	+0,88	-0,03
Potassium Erythrocytes	-0,102	-0,057	-0,006	+0,38	+0,04	-0,12	-0,29
Glucose Plasma	-0,047	-0,077	-0,150	+0,62	+0,29	+0,31	+0,30
Sodium Erythrocytes	currently not in the model			+0,23	+0,35	+0,24	-0,37
Sodium Excretion	currently not in the model			+0,79	+0,59	+0,17	-0,19
Chloride Excretion	currently not in the model			+0,70	+0,47	-0,09	+0,10
Osmolality Urine	currently not in the model			+0,37	-0,06	-0,26	-0,21
Urea Plasma	0,170	0,235	0,262	-1,24	+0,78	+1,09	+1,15
Magnesium Excretion	currently not in the model			-0,24	+0,15	+0,61	+0,83
Root 2 (24,0 %)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-1,88	+0,28	+1,63	-1,08
Magnesium Plasma	-0,142	0,426	-0,585	-0,07	-0,17	+0,64	-0,72
Phosphates Plasma	-0,193	0,411	0,132	+0,28	+0,85	+1,02	-0,57
Calcium Excretion	-0,023	0,225	0,195	-0,20	+0,83	+0,90	-0,01
Potassium Plasma	-0,094	0,183	-0,017	-0,85	-0,69	-0,51	-1,39
Creatinine Plasma	currently not in the model			-0,93	+0,35	+1,02	+0,34
Sodium Plasma	currently not in the model			+0,16	+0,02	+0,43	-0,23
Chloride Plasma	currently not in the model			-0,08	-0,33	+0,07	-0,50
Calcium Plasma	currently not in the model			-0,42	-0,65	-0,92	-0,56
Root 3 (4,1 %)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-0,53	+0,71	-0,48	-0,03
Phosphates Excretion	-0,038	0,108	0,446	-0,06	+0,52	+0,16	-0,02
Urea Excretion	-0,101	0,085	0,199	+0,46	+0,71	+0,41	-0,19
Potassium Excretion	currently not in the model			+0,03	+0,21	-0,05	-0,03

Table 4

Squares of Mahalanobis distances between clusters (above the diagonal) and F- criteria (df = 11,5) and p-levels (below the diagonal)

Clusters	S-Un-	S+Un+	SnUn+	Sn+U+
S-Un-	0	46	18	21
S+Un+	19,2 10-6	0	24	12
SnUn+	10,7 10-6	10,6 10-6	0	5
Sn+U+	13,3 10-6	3,6 10-4	3,0 0,005	0

Table 5

Coefficients and constants of classification functions for metabolic accompaniment of clusters of uric acid metabolism

Variable	S-Un-p = 0,250	S+Un+p = 0,150	SnUn+p = 0,283	Sn+U+p = 0,317
Uricemia	0,032	0,060	0,043	0,049
Magnesium Plasma	0,443	4,229	6,779	3,770
Phosphates Plasma	15,39	21,65	23,18	23,98
Phosphates Excretion	1,478	1,226	1,369	1,644
Potassium Plasma	11,63	14,81	15,32	15,27
Urea Plasma	0,059	-0,512	0,466	0,122
Potassium Erythrocytes	2,858	3,304	2,905	3,069
Creatinine Excretion	-1,476	-1,316	-1,126	-1,396
Glucose Plasma	11,99	13,56	11,49	12,25
Urea Excretion	0,044	0,084	0,060	0,064
Calcium Excretion	-1,650	-3,296	-2,263	-2,446
Constant	-182,7	-268,9	-220,4	-237,3

phates and calcium with urine. Other registered parameters of metabolism, primarily uricosuria and urine osmolality, as well as excretion of sodium, chloride, magnesium and phosphates as well as plasma levels of creatinine, calcium, chloride and sodium, and the latter in erythrocytes, were outside the discriminant model.

The identifying information contained in the 11 discriminant variables is condensed into three roots. The first root contains 71,9 % of the discriminant power ($r^* = 0,915$; Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,047$; $\chi^2(33) = 158$; $p < 10^{-6}$), second — 24,0 % ($r^* = 0,795$; Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,286$; $\chi^2(20) = 65$; $p = 10^{-6}$), and the third only 4,1 % and, moreover, is insignificant ($r^* = 0,474$; Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,775$; $\chi^2(9) = 13$; $p = 0,158$).

Further, on the basis of the coefficients given in the Table 2 (see the appendix), the individual root values were calculated with subsequent visualization of cluster members in their information field.

In the Table 3 metabolic parameters are grouped and ranked according to their structural coefficients, and together with discriminant variables, variables that did not enter the mod-

are also considered.

Fig. 1 shows that the extreme left zone of the first root axis is occupied by

Table 6

Classification matrix for uric acid exchange clusters

Clusters	Percent Correct	S+Un+	Sn+U+	SnUn+	S-Un-
		p = 0,150	p = 0,317	p = 0,283	p = 0,250
S+Un+	100	9	0	0	0
Sn+U+	94,7	0	18	1	0
SnUn+	88,2	0	2	15	0
S-Un-	100	0	0	0	15
Total	95,0	9	20	16	15

Rows: observed classifications; columns: predicted classifications

Table 7

Matrix of correlations between parameters of uric acid and electrolyte-nitrogen exchanges

Variable	Uricemia	Uricosuria
CrE	0,15	0,39
Diur	0,09	0,54
CrP	-0,28	0,13
KE	0,09	0,46
MgE	-0,30	-0,06
CaE	-0,03	0,33
PE	0,02	0,50
UreaE	0,12	0,35
UreaP	-0,31	0,06
KP	0,05	0,20

Table 8

Regression model for metabolic parameters and uricemia

N = 60	R = 0,509; R ² = 0,259; Adjusted R ² = 0,219; F (3,6) = 6,5; p = 0,0007					
	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t (56)	p-value
Intcpt			926,31	179,17	5,17	0,000003
Cr E	0,353	0,127	31,84	11,41	2,79	0,007176
Mg E	-0,394	0,128	-60,43	19,55	-3,09	0,003108
Urea P	-0,282	0,117	-39,98	16,62	-2,41	0,019495

Table 9

Regression model for metabolic parameters and uricosuria

N = 60	R = 0,621; R ² = 0,386; Adjusted R ² = 0,329 F (5,5) = 6,8; p = 0,00006					
	Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t (54)	p-value
Intcpt			-0,071	1,853	-0,04	0,969
Cr Excr	-0,404	0,238	-0,268	0,158	-1,70	0,096
Diurese	1,023	0,452	4,301	1,900	2,26	0,028
K Excr	0,338	0,144	0,011	0,005	2,34	0,023
P Excr	-0,388	0,350	-0,234	0,211	-1,11	0,272
K Plasma	0,123	0,111	0,496	0,450	1,10	0,275

members of the S+Un+ cluster. Such localization reflects the combination of hyperuricemia with increased (and maximal for the sample) levels of creatinine excretion, erythrocyte potassium and glycemia, and a reduced level of urea in the plasma. Worthy of attention are the maximum normal levels of uricosuria, erythrocyte natriuresis, and urine osmolality for the sample, and elevated levels of natriuria and chlorideuria, instead of minimal normal magniuria. The opposite polar position is occupied by the members of the S-Un- cluster, which are characterized by a combination of hypouricemia with a reduced content of potassium in erythrocytes, normal, but minimal for the sample, uricosuria, creatinineuria, and glycemia, instead, maximally elevated levels of urea in plasma and magnesia. Members of the other two clusters occupy an intermediate position along the axis of the first radical and are partially mixed.

Mixing also takes place along the axis of the second radical, but to a lesser extent. At the same time, members of the SnUn+ cluster are characterized by maximally increased levels of magnesium, phosphatemia, and calciuria (as well as abnormal creatinineemia and natriemia) in combination with minimally reduced potassium (as well as maximally reduced calcium).

An additional unclear demarcation of these clusters occurs along the axis of the third radical, due to the maximally increased excretion of phosphates and urea (as well as potassium) in the members of the Sn+U+ cluster.

The application of classification functions (Table 5) enables the retrospective identification of the first two clusters without error, and the other two with 1 and 2 errors, which gives a total accuracy of 95,0 % (Table 6).

At the last stage, we will analyze the connections between the parameters of uric acid and electrolyte-nitrogen exchange-

Fig. 1. Scattering of individual values of the first and second (top) and first and third (bottom) discriminant metabolic roots of rats of different clusters

es. The correlation matrix shows that uricemia is significantly associated with plasma levels of urea and creatinine and magnesia (Table 7).

However, when constructing a regression model by stepwise exclusion, the program left creatinineuria in the model, excluding creatinineemia. As a result, the determination rate was 26 % (Table 8).

Instead, the connections of uricosuria are more numerous and stronger. The descending series consists of: daily diuresis, urinary excretion of phosphates, potassium, creatinine, urea and calcium. Interestingly, with stepwise elimination, the last two parameters were not included in the regression model, while plasma potassium was. The rate of determination of the listed parameters by uricosuria is 39 % (Table 9).

According to the results of the canon-

Table 10

Factor structure of canonical roots of uric acid and neuro-endocrine adaptation factors

Variable	left set
	R
Uricosuria	-0,910
Uricemia	-0,070
Variable	right set
	R
Creatinine Excretion	-0,490
Diuresis	-0,765
Creatinine Plasma	-0,373
Potassium Excretion	-0,639
Magnesium Excretion	-0,098
Calcium Excretion	-0,519
Phosphates Excretion	-0,745
Urea Excretion	-0,460
Urea Plasma	-0,289
Potassium Plasma	-0,278

ical correlation analysis, the total determining influence of the parameters of uric acid exchange (due to the significant advantage of uricosuria over uricemia) on the constellation of parameters of electrolyte and nitrogen exchange reaches 56 % (Fig.).

The factor loadings on the metabolic canonical root indicate that diuresis and excretion of phosphates and potassium are the most positively determined; calcium, creatinine and urea excretion are less determined; creatinine, urea and potassium levels in plasma are even less determined, and magnesiumuria is the least determined (Table 10).

Conclusion

Uric acid is naturally associated with the state of electrolytes and nitrogenous metabolites exchange in healthy female rats.

A detailed discussion will be conducted after the publication of the results of a similar study in humans.

Conformity To Ethical Standards

Experiments on animals have been

$R=0,751$; $R^2=0,563$; $\chi^2_{(20)}=65$; $p<10^{-6}$; Λ Prime=0,292

Fig.2. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between uricosuria and uricemia (X axis) and metabolic parameters (Y axis) of female rats

carried out in accordance with the provisions of the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, revised and supplemented in 2002 by the Directives of the National Committees for Ethics in Scientific Research.

The conduct of experiments was approved by the Ethics Committee of the SR Institute of Medicine of Transport. The modern rules for the maintenance and use of laboratory animals complying with the principles of the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for scientific experiments and needs are observed (Strasbourg, 1985).

References

1. Gozhenko AI, Smaglyi VS, Korda IV, Zukow W, Popovych IL. Cluster analysis of uric acid exchange parameters in female rats. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2019; 9 (11): 277-286.
2. Gozhenko AI, Smaglyi VS, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow W, Popovych IL. Features of immune status in different states of uric acid metabolism in female rats. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2019; 9 (12): 167-180.
3. Gozhenko AI, Smaglyi VS, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow W, Popovych IL. Functional relationships between parameters of uric acid exchange and immunity in female rats. *Actual problems of transport medicine*. 2019; 4 (58): 123-131.
4. Smaglyi VS, Gozhenko AI, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow W, Kovbasnyuk MM, Popovych IL. Variants of uric acid metabolism and their immune and microbiota accompaniments in

- patients with neuroendocrine-immune complex dysfunction. Actual problems of transport medicine. 2020; 1 (59): 114–125.
5. Gozhenko AI, Smagliy VS, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow W, Kovbasnyuk MM, Popovych IL. Relationships between parameters of uric acid exchange and immunity as well as microbiota in patients with neuroendocrine-immune complex dysfunction. Journal of Education, Health and Sport. 2020; 10 (1): 165-175.
 6. Gozhenko AI, Smagliy VS, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow W, Kovbasnyuk MM, Popovych IL. Relationships between changes in uric acid parameters metabolism and parameters of immunity and microbiota in patients with neuroendocrine-immune complex dysfunction. Journal of Education, Health and Sport. 2020; 10 (2): 212-222.
 7. Popovych IL, Bombushkar IS, Badiuk NS, Korda IV, Zukow W, Gozhenko AI. Features of the state of neuro-endocrine factors of adaptation under different options of uric acid metabolism in healthy female rats. Journal of Education, Health and Sport. 2020; 10 (3): 352-362.
 8. Ivassivka SV, Popovych IL, Aksentiychuk BI, Flyunt IS. Physiological Activity of Uric Acid and its Role in the Mechanism of Action of Naf-tussya Water [in Ukrainian]. Kyiv: Computer-press; 2004: 163.
 9. Goryachkovskiy AM. Clinical Biochemistry [in Russian]. Odessa: Astroprint; 1998: 608.
 10. Klecka WR. Discriminant Analysis [trans. from English in Russian] (Seventh Printing, 1986). In: Factor, Discriminant and Cluster Analysis. Moskva: Finansy i Statistika; 1989: 78-138.

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